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NEET in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022

Between 2018 and 2022 they decreased by 17.31%

Istat calculates the value of people who do not work or study, i.e. NEETs. NEET are defined as the percentage of people aged 15-29 neither employed nor in education and training out of the total number of people aged 15-29. The data refers to the period between 2018 and 2022 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of young people who do not study and do not work in 2022. Sicily is in first place for the value of young people who do not study and do not work with a value of 32.4, followed by Campania with an amount of 29.7 and Calabria with 26. In the middle of the table is Lazio with a value of 17, followed by Piedmont with an amount of 15.4 and Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 15.3. The Marche closes the ranking with an amount of 13.1 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of 12.2 units and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 10.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change of young people who do not study and do not work between 2018 and 2022. Valle d'Aosta is in first place by value of the percentage change of the percentage change of young people who do not study and do not work between 2018 and 2022 with a value of -6.13%, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of -6.25%, and Lombardy with an amount of -9.33%. In the middle of the table are Sicily with an amount of -15.63%, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with an amount of -16.00%, and Campania with -17.27%. Lazio closes the ranking with -23.42%, followed by Umbria with -23.81% and Liguria with an amount of -25.25%. Between 2018 and 2022 the value of young people who do not study or work on average in the Italian regions went from 22 to 18.2 with a value of -17.31%.

Young people who do not study or work in the Italian macro-regions. Young people who do not study and do not work have decreased in Northern Italy from an amount of 15.50 to a value of 13.50 or a reduction of 12.90% between 2018 and 2022. Young people who do not study and do not work in the North-West decreased from an amount of 16.10 units to a value of 14.20 units or a reduction of -1.90 units equal to -11.80% between 2018 and 2022. The young people who do not study or work in the North-East went from an amount of 14.70 units in 2018 to a value of 12.50 units in 2022, or a reduction of -2.20 units equal to a value of -14.97%. Young people who do not study or work decreased in Central Italy from an amount of 19.40 units to a value of 15.30 units or equal to an amount of -4.10 units equal to a value of -21.13 % between 2018 and 2022. Young people who do not study or work decreased in the South from an amount of 33.60 units to a value of 27.90 units or equal to a value of -5.70 units equal to a value of -16.96% between 2018 and 2022. Young people who do not study or work in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 32.50 units to a value of 26.90 units or equal to a value of -5.60 units equal to an amount of -17.23% between 2018 and 2022. Young people who do not study or work in the Islands have decreased from an amount of 36.10 units

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to a value of 30, 10 units or equal to a value of -6.00 units equal to an amount of -16.62% between 2018 and 2022. The value of young people who do not study and do not work has decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below is proposed a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows two clusters:

- *Cluster 1:* Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Tuscany, Molise, Umbria, Basilicata, Piedmont, Liguria, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta;
- *Cluster 2:* Campania, Puglia, Calabria, Sicily, Sardinia.

Looking at the composition of the clusters we can notice that the value of cluster 2 tends to dominate the value of cluster 1 or $C2 > C1$. Specifically we can note that cluster 2 is made up of almost all the southern regions with the exception of Basilicata, Abruzzo and Molise. It therefore follows that there is a significant gap between the regions of Central-Northern Italy and the regions of Southern Italy in terms of the number of young people who do not study or work.

Conclusions. The value of young people who do not study or work decreased in all Italian regions between 2018 and 2022. The regions in which there was a significant reduction in the value of NEETs are Calabria with -21.67%, Sardinia with a value of -22.46%, Lazio with a value of -23.42%, Umbria with -23.81% and Liguria with -25.25%. The value of NEETs tends to be high in southern regions characterized by a lower demand for work and a lower offer of university and professional training. It is very likely, however, that the real values, net of the underground and illegal economy, are much lower than the relevant ones, as illegal work appears to be very widespread in the southern regions. In any case, even net of illegal work, the situation of the southern economies remains behind. In fact, it is very likely that young people who do not study or work have problems effectively entering the job market and could experience forms of permanent unemployment and cultural, human and civil underdevelopment, having neither access to income nor to knowledge useful for interpret what exists.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Neet nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2018 ed il 2022				
Regione	2018	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 17,60	★ 15,40	★ -2,20	★ -12,50
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 16,30	★ 15,30	★ -1,00	★ -6,13
<i>Liguria</i>	★ 19,80	★ 14,80	★ -5,00	★ -25,25
<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 15,00	★ 13,60	★ -1,40	★ -9,33
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ 12,50	★ 10,50	★ -2,00	★ -16,00
<i>Veneto</i>	★ 14,80	★ 13,10	★ -1,70	★ -11,49
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 14,40	★ 13,50	★ -0,90	★ -6,25
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 15,30	★ 12,20	★ -3,10	★ -20,26
<i>Toscana</i>	★ 16,00	★ 13,80	★ -2,20	★ -13,75
<i>Umbria</i>	★ 18,90	★ 14,40	★ -4,50	★ -23,81
<i>Marche</i>	★ 16,60	★ 13,10	★ -3,50	★ -21,08
<i>Lazio</i>	★ 22,20	★ 17,00	★ -5,20	★ -23,42
<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 20,50	★ 17,90	★ -2,60	★ -12,68
<i>Molise</i>	★ 25,80	★ 20,90	★ -4,90	★ -18,99
<i>Campania</i>	★ 35,90	★ 29,70	★ -6,20	★ -17,27
<i>Puglia</i>	★ 30,40	★ 26,00	★ -4,40	★ -14,47
<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 26,00	★ 20,60	★ -5,40	★ -20,77
<i>Calabria</i>	★ 36,00	★ 28,20	★ -7,80	★ -21,67
<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 38,40	★ 32,40	★ -6,00	★ -15,63
<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 27,60	★ 21,40	★ -6,20	★ -22,46

Neet nelle Regioni Italiane

Regioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	★ 15,50	★ 14,40	★ 17,10	★ 17,00	★ 13,50	★ -2,00	★ -12,90
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	★ 16,10	★ 15,40	★ 18,70	★ 18,70	★ 14,20	★ -1,90	★ -11,80
<i>Nord-est</i>	★ 14,70	★ 13,00	★ 15,00	★ 14,70	★ 12,50	★ -2,20	★ -14,97
<i>Centro</i>	★ 19,40	★ 18,00	★ 20,20	★ 19,60	★ 15,30	★ -4,10	★ -21,13
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	★ 33,60	★ 32,90	★ 33,30	★ 32,20	★ 27,90	★ -5,70	★ -16,96
<i>Sud</i>	★ 32,50	★ 31,60	★ 32,20	★ 31,50	★ 26,90	★ -5,60	★ -17,23
<i>Isole</i>	★ 36,10	★ 35,80	★ 35,80	★ 33,60	★ 30,10	★ -6,00	★ -16,62
<i>Italia</i>	★ 23,20	★ 22,10	★ 23,70	★ 23,10	★ 19,00	★ -4,20	★ -18,10
<i>Media</i>	★ 23,89	★ 22,90	★ 24,50	★ 23,80	★ 19,93	★ -3,96	★ -16,59

Neet nelle Regioni Italiane		
Rank	Regione	2022
1	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 32,4
2	<i>Campania</i>	★ 29,7
3	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 28,2
4	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 26
5	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 21,4
6	<i>Molise</i>	★ 20,9
7	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 20,6
8	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 17,9
9	<i>Lazio</i>	☆ 17
10	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 15,4
11	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	☆ 15,3
12	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 14,8
13	<i>Umbria</i>	☆ 14,4
14	<i>Toscana</i>	☆ 13,8
15	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 13,6
16	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 13,5
17	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 13,1
18	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 13,1
19	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	☆ 12,2
20	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	☆ 10,5

